

Doctor Alvaro Taveras Franco (EscID: 1560625)

Email: alvarotaveras73@gmail.com

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Title : Electrocardiographic markers of obstructive sleep apnea: association of rSr' pattern with disease presence and severity in a hispanic cohort

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Doctor C. Vargas-Reynoso ⁽¹⁾, Doctor A. Taveras Franco ⁽²⁾, Doctor E. Crousett ⁽²⁾, Doctor O. Ruiz ⁽²⁾, Doctor L. Cruz ⁽²⁾

⁽¹⁾ Medical Union Clinic, Santiago de los Caballeros, Dominican Republic, ⁽²⁾ Metropolitan Hospital of Santiago, Santiago de los Caballeros, Dominican Republic

Background: Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a highly prevalent condition associated with significant cardiovascular morbidity. Early identification remains challenging, particularly in resource-limited settings. Electrocardiography (ECG) represents a widely available and low-cost tool, but its role in OSA detection remains incompletely defined.

Purpose: To evaluate the association between ECG abnormalities and the presence and severity of OSA, with a focus on the rSr' pattern in right precordial leads.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective study of 670 adults who underwent overnight polysomnography and standard 12-lead ECG. Patients were categorized based on OSA diagnosis and Apnea-Hypopnea Index (AHI). ECG findings, including rSr' pattern in V1-V2, deep S waves in V5-V6, prolonged QRS duration, and atrial fibrillation, were compared between groups. Multivariable logistic regression was performed to identify independent predictors of OSA.

Results: Among 670 patients, those with OSA demonstrated a significantly higher prevalence of ECG abnormalities compared with non-OSA individuals. The rSr' pattern in V1-V2 was significantly more frequent in patients with OSA ($p < 0.05$), along with increased prevalence of deep S waves in V5-V6, prolonged QRS duration, and atrial fibrillation. In multivariable analysis, the presence of rSr' in V1-V2 was independently associated with OSA (OR 2.64; 95% CI 1.27-5.50), representing a strong electrocardiographic marker of disease. Deep S waves in lateral leads showed a non-significant trend toward association. Additionally, the use of angiotensin receptor blockers and beta-blockers was independently associated with OSA, likely reflecting a higher burden of underlying cardiovascular disease.

These findings were consistent across increasing OSA severity categories based on AHI, suggesting a potential role of ECG markers not only in detection but also in risk stratification.

Conclusion: ECG abnormalities, particularly the rSr' pattern in right precordial leads, are associated with the presence of OSA and may serve as a simple, low-cost screening tool. These findings support the potential role of ECG in early identification of OSA, especially in resource-limited settings, and warrant further prospective validation.